

Diffusion of Artificial Intelligence in Human Resource Domain with Specific Reference to Recruitment Function: A Literature Review Study

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Abstract:- Artificial intelligence is the buzzword around the world in the current times. It has migrated into a number of fields, including the core areas of business like marketing, finance, and human resource management. The ability of a computer or a robot controlled by a computer to do tasks that typically require human knowledge and discernment is known as artificial intellect (AI). The application of AI is helping transfer the repetitive and mundane tasks to the computer so that humans can concentrate on the activities which need human intervention and cannot be performed by computers or robots. Human Resource functions are a gamut of all the activities performed throughout the life cycle of an employee starting from hiring new employees, ensuring their performance and growth, and their exit from the organization. In the list of activities performed by the human resource function, many activities are too much time taking, repetitive and monotonous. Such tasks can be delegated to robots, or the use of AI in such tasks will free up a lot of time for HR experts so they can focus on more inventive and fruitful tasks. The function of recruiting is one of the main HR activities. This study reviews the research from the last five years with a particular emphasis on the use of AI in the recruitment function of human resource management. Understanding the dissemination of AI in recruitment functions would be made easier through the analysis of such material.

Keywords:- Artificial Intelligence, Human Resource Management, Recruitment.

I. INTRODUCTION

We are at the beginning of a revolution that will fundamentally change the way we behave, live, and work. It's amazing to observe how the industry has evolved from the first industrial revolution in the late 1800s to the third, which started in the middle of the 20th century and was driven by new information technology and automation. The fourth industrial revolution, often known as Industry 4.0, is the era of artificial intelligence (AI) and the Internet of Things (IoT). Because digitization is advancing so quickly, organizations need to be ready for the various changes that technology will bring. A revolution that will completely alter the way we act, live, and work is just getting started. From the first industrial revolution in the late 1800s to the third, which began in the middle of the 20th century and was propelled by new information technology and automation, the industry has undergone an astounding evolution. Industry 4.0, also referred to as the fourth industrial

revolution, is the era of artificial intelligence (AI) and the Internet of Things (IoT). Organizations need to be prepared for the different changes that technology will bring because digitization is developing so swiftly.

(Dimple Agarwal, Josh Bersin, Gaurav Lahiri, and Jeff Schwartz, 2018) assert that automated human resources recruiting is streamlined by artificial intelligence applications like problem-solving, a data-driven function. Future work will be given higher priority across the market, with employers and employees considering knowledge, skills, and traits to stay competitive in the market for long-term sustainability. The industry is now considering using artificial intelligence in the hiring process. The recruitment industry is getting closer to integrating artificial intelligence into the hiring process by taking into account previous studies, such as the study of artificial intelligence covered in earlier years.

In fact, according to several studies, AI is involved in the hiring process (Upadhyay & Khandelwal, 2018), (Bullhorn, 2018), (Paradox, 2018). Considering this context, the author's objective is to draw attention to a component of the hiring process that has gotten little attention in the literature but is crucial to HRM from a strategic perspective. In fact, the author thought that successful recruiting strategies were essential for organizational success. Therefore, understanding the difficulties associated with the hiring process can help to improve hiring practices, making a talent allocator more skilled and efficient. Based on the results of a systematic study, the paper will explore how much the literature has addressed the spread of artificial intelligence in the hiring process.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Using qualitative and exploratory research methods, Edward Tristram Albert (2019) investigated the present use of artificial intelligence (AI) in the recruitment and selection of applicants. His study examined the degree, pace, and possible applications of AI technologies across the recruiting process. To ascertain how many of the AI applications domains listed in the literature review are being used in practice, a thorough literature review was followed by primary research in the form of semi-structured thematic interviews with different types of R&S specialists, including HR managers, consultants, and academics. They discovered that there are places where AI applications can be used in all 11 stages of the R&S Process. And the ones that are now used most frequently are task automation technologies, screening software, and chatbots. Additionally, they were

able to comprehend that larger, tech-focused, or inventive businesses are more likely to utilise these AI solutions. Finally, despite the exponential growth of AI use, corporations are still hesitant to invest in that technology for R&S, indicating that they have not yet reached an inflection point. His study gave a thorough review of the state of AI in R&S and opened up numerous potential for academic research, both qualitative and quantitative, which will be useful for researchers and practitioners trying to quickly get a full grasp of AI in R&S.

AI-assisted hiring aids are now necessary rather than just pleasant to have. Black and Esch's paper, "AI-enabled recruiting: What is it and how should a manager use it?," looks at the reasons behind this move. (2019). As competitive advantages have changed from tangible to intangible assets, human capital has emerged from the background to take center stage. Second, digital human capital recruiting has emerged from the background as the economic and social landscapes have been transformed by digitization. Third, managers shouldn't disregard or delay incorporating recent and upcoming advancements in AI-enabled recruiting since they have increased recruiting effectiveness to the point where they should not be done so. Key strategic activities managers must undertake to benefit from AI-assisted recruiting systems have been outlined, along with the obstacles that have turned them from desirable to crucial.

In their article "Artificial Intelligence Chatbots are New Recruiters" that was published in "International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications," Nawas and Gomes (2019) evaluated the impact of artificial intelligence chatbots on the hiring process. They looked into how chatbots may give services to entice prospects to participate in the hiring process. The study sought to determine how chatbots were affecting the hiring process overall. The study used secondary sources and data from websites, peer-reviewed articles, and conceptual papers. After conducting study, it was discovered that artificial intelligence chatbots are very effective tools in the hiring process and will aid in developing industry-specific recruitment tactics. It also focused on resolutions to the complex issues in the process of recruitment. Researchers' interest in the amalgamation of the artificial intelligence hiring process is growing, but there is still need for further investigation.

In his work "How Far Have We Come with The Study of Artificial Intelligence for Recruitment Process," Nishad Niwas (2019) did a systematic review of the opinions from a number of referred publications, periodicals, and websites. The study's findings complemented research on the AI-based hiring process by fostering a more comprehensive understanding of the subject and adjacent fields.

Artificial intelligence (AI) is a developing technology that is being utilised to improve the effectiveness of HR processes across a number of commercial disciplines. However, there aren't many scholarly studies that look at how AI affects hiring. With an emphasis on recruiting and selection, George, Thomas, and Anson's research from 2021

attempted to critically analyse the various roles that AI plays in HR tasks. The paper also made an effort to define AI and ideas associated with it in the context of human resources. The study's literature evaluation on artificial intelligence in hiring (AIHR) led to the discovery of 200 research articles on the topic that were published between 2010 and 2020.

Alall et al. (2021) conducted research to examine how digital technologies improve the next steps of the hiring process, including talent identification, selection, and retention. A new and diverse phenomenon called e-recruitment begins with the identification of candidates on social media, progresses to the gamification of hiring and job interviews using chatbots, and concludes with the matching of a candidate with a position using artificial intelligence. These tools are especially helpful for ethical organisations that want to hire not just talented workers but also staff members whose attitudes and beliefs align with their mission. Grounded theory, participant observation, and gathering qualitative data form the methodology's foundation. Several recruitment-related technologies were analysed, contrasted, and combined in a multiple case study, including a social network with LinkedIn, a MOOC with Udacity, a serious game called Reveal from L'Oréal, a chatbot named Ari from TextRecruit, and a massive data analysis matching system with Randstad tech. The debate focused on the individual strengths and weaknesses of these instruments as well as how they converge through a progressive integration that causes an aberration in recruitment. To help recruiters implement e-recruitment, managerial tips were developed.

Despite the fact that many businesses now use artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) in their hiring processes, research indicates that candidates may not be amenable to AI/ML-based selection procedures. In the current study, Gonzales et al. (2022) looked into how businesses could reduce adverse reactions to AI/ML-based selection processes. In two between-subjects experiments, they gathered online samples of participants (undergraduate students and Prolific panellists, respectively) and showed them vignettes illustrating alternative selection processes. In Study 1, they altered (a) whether the system was run by a human, AI/ML, or a combination of both (an "augmented" method), and (b) the selection process in Study 2. (Screening is the last step). The results showed that participants responded more positively to augmented and human-based tactics than to AI/ML-based approaches, which were further influenced by participants' prior levels of AI familiarity. They sought to replicate their results in Study 2 by employing a particular methodology (selecting hotel managers) and application approach (handling interview recordings). They found that participants' sentiments of the augmented approach were significantly influenced by their familiarity with AI. Their conclusions have an impact on who should use AI/ML-based procedures and how they should be executed.

In order to ascertain the stages at which organisations are using AI in recruitment practises in Sweden and the attitudes of recruiters and recruits toward the use of AI in the recruitment process in the Sweden organisational

context, Aysha Khatun Lisa and Valerie RostanTalla Simo (2021) used a qualitative approach with semi-structured interviews with three recruiters and five recruits in Sweden. The results show that the majority of businesses employ AI in the initial phases of the hiring process. However, more than 50% of staff at some companies are hired using AI. Additionally, they learned that the study's recruits had a positive outlook and indicated that they would be fine with AI being employed in conventional hiring. Additionally, they welcome innovation since they think that in order to compete in this industry, it is imperative to accept new technology. They further claimed that AI-assisted hiring will help to eliminate bias and guarantee fair hiring.

In their article "Antecedents and outcomes of artificial intelligence adoption and application in the workplace: The socio-technical system theory perspective," Xinying Yu, Xu, and Ashton (2022) developed a theoretically grounded conceptual framework on the socio-technical system theory that captures the essence of AI's impact on the workplace. Artificial Intelligence (AI) is now more prevalent in HR Information Systems and Human Resource Management Systems (HRMS) as a result of Human Resource Management (HRM) digitization (HRIS). Recruiting, employee performance reviews and satisfaction, wage and benefit analyses, best practise analysis, disciplinary management, and employee training and development systems are just a few tactical activities that are increasingly using AI. We plan to review literature and public sources that cover the application of AI in HRM in order to have a better grasp of this trend. Using a systematic literature review technique, this study identifies which tactical HRIS (T-HRIS) components are discussed in the literature and how each T-HRIS component is portrayed. This study sheds light on the tactical HRM/HRIS components that are given attention and identifies areas for future research needs.

In their 2019 study, Parry and Battista looked at the effects of current and emerging technologies on the workforce as well as the role of the human resource (HR) function in helping people and companies adapt to these changes. Evidence suggests that businesses are utilising cutting-edge tools like robots and artificial intelligence to automate routine, uncomplicated tasks and predictive algorithms to make complex decisions more quickly and accurately. Additionally, more and more flexible working methods, like telecommuting and virtual work, are being implemented thanks to new technologies. However, this will provide difficulties for HR professionals, who must help workers upgrade their abilities in order to compete in the future workplace and develop solutions to deal with any

potential detrimental consequences of networking and insecure employment situations on quality of work life.

This study looked into the adoption of artificial intelligence (AI) in business recruiting procedures in the context of a new workplace setting and provided insights on the topic. Pillai and Shivathanu (2020) addressed goals by looking at the decision-making criteria for AI adoption through three studies that employed the Delphi method. Then, two multi-criteria decision-making procedures were employed to examine the amount of AI used in recruiting: the analytical hierarchy process to construct weights of the criterion and fuzzy methodology for ranking preference by resemblance to ideal answer. The results demonstrated that while contemplating the use of AI in the hiring process, human resource managers should give high priority to information security and return on investment. It was found that sourcing and initial screening for jobs are good places for AI adoption. Furthermore, it has been shown that between before and after the COVID-19 pandemic crisis started, the appropriateness of the recruiting stage at which AI may be utilised changed.

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III. METHODOLOGY USED IN THE PAPER

This study is a review of the literature. About 35 research papers were reviewed for this study, of which 20 were used in the literature review based on the use of artificial intelligence in the field of human resource management, specifically with reference to the recruitment function. This study only uses secondary data, and the majority of the publications published in SAGE, EMERALD, and SPRINGER journals over the previous five years were used in the data gathering. In order to comprehend the dissemination of Artificial Intelligence in the field of HRM with particular reference to the actions carried out in the recruitment function, the collected papers were reviewed of the variables analyzed.

IV. DISCUSSION AND FINDINGS

Sr. No	Name of the Article	Variables	Methodology adopted and Findings
1	Artificial Intelligence in Tactical Human Resource Management: A Systematic Literature Review	AI and In the context of complete HR domain	Using a systematic literature review methodology, this study examines which tactical HRIS (T-HRIS) components are mentioned in the literature and how each T-HRIS component is described. The application of AI in tactical operations such as hiring, employee performance assessment and satisfaction, wage and benefit analysis, analysis of best practises, disciplinary management, and employee training and development systems is on the rise.
2	The impact of emerging technologies on work: a review of the evidence and implications for the human resource function	Emerging technologies and its implications on HR function	Using secondary data, this study examines how new technologies are affecting the workplace and how HR can help people and organisations deal with these changes. Additionally, new technologies are rapidly being used to support the adoption of more flexible working patterns, such as gig and virtual labour. However, HR professionals will have a number of challenges in assisting workers in updating their skills to compete in the future workplace and dealing with potential adverse effects of increased connectivity and unstable working conditions on employee well-being.
3	Evolution of Artificial Intelligence Research in Human Resources	AI in HR domain -Evolution	Based on a quantitative descriptive study of journals and proceedings in the Library of Online Knowledge (B-on) database, it offers a glimpse of AI-based HR research from 2000 to 2018. The use of artificial intelligence in the subject of human resources is covered in 32 research articles. Three time periods were created out of the 18-year period under study as a didactic tool and to make the analysis simpler to understand (First decade, Reduction Period, and Period of Growth). As a result, it was discovered that utilisation of AI in human resources is dispersed and that there are few studies on the subject.
4	Impact of Artificial Intelligence on HR practices in the UAE	AI, HR practices, UAE	A mixed-method approach was used to investigate and test the study's questions. Surveys, semi-structured interviews, and research designs were completed for both. People in HR and AI were asked to participate in the study as volunteers. Thematic analysis and PLS-SEM were used to analyse the data (Partial least squares path modeling). Positive and significant outcomes were obtained from the planned training and development process (0.2310.021), the tactical performance appraisal and AI integration (0.7190.000), and the AI integration and effective HR practises (0.2040.131). The ease of use has a negative and negligible effect on the integration of AI and efficient HR procedures. The digitalization of HR tasks relies heavily on AI.
5	Artificial intelligence and human workers interaction at the team level: a conceptual assessment of the challenges and potential HRM strategies	AI and Human Workers interaction at the Team level	In their research, Arslan et al. (2021) discovered that human workers and robots interact and cooperate in a range of organisational tasks and industries where they both function as team members. Modern firms' HRM departments must deal with employees' concerns about working with AI, particularly those related to potential job loss and the challenging dynamics of building trust between human employees and AI-enabled robots as team members.
6	Perceived trust in artificial intelligence technologies: A preliminary study	Trust in AI	The current study is a conceptual work that synthesises data from several literature streams to provide a very complete yet critical analysis of how AI (particularly robots) and HRM interact in modern enterprises. The authors found that organisational support measures such a supportive environment, training opportunities, and ensuring a proper technological competence level are crucial before organising human workers in teams with robots. Finally, they found that performance evaluation in teams that comprise both humans and AI poses one of the most challenging challenges for HRM (including robots). This study examined users' views of

			task complexity, task trustworthiness, and application performance when adopting AI-based technologies.
7	Exploring Artificial Intelligence Applications in Human Resource Management	AI, HRM domain	23 pertinent papers were discovered when searching the Scopus online database from 1991 to 2020 and used in the study as a sample. In order to improve efficiency and effectiveness in their human resource management operations and satisfy consumer requests, organisations can apply artificial intelligence in nine different areas of human resource management tasks, according to the report. Other facets of human resource management could be covered by the research.
8	Integration of Artificial Intelligence in Human Resource	AI and HR domain	The study used an interview method with the use of tailored questions to target HR professionals in corporate settings and primarily depended on secondary data. For the study to better understand AI applications, 117 professionals provided primary data. Many businesses are seeking to integrate AI in HR despite the obstacles because the advantages outweigh the difficulties.
9	AI adoption by human resource management: a study of its antecedents and impact on HR system effectiveness	AI, Impact, HR system effectiveness	This study suggests a model to explain the variables affecting HRM's adoption of AI. The proposed model makes use of the task-organization-environment and task-technology fit models. Two-step partial least squares-based structural equation modelling was used to test the model (PLS-SEM). Information was gathered from 210 HRM employees working in IT companies in the Delhi-NCR area (only senior-level or specialised HR positions). Analysis of the literature indicates that organisational preparation, perceived benefits, and technical readiness all have an impact on the adoption of AI, which can increase the efficiency of HR systems. The recommended model is supported by the PLS-SEM findings, which also support all hypothesised correlations.
10	Adoption of artificial intelligence (AI) for talent acquisition in IT/ITeS organizations	AI, Talent acquisition, IT and ITES Organizations	The use of AI technology for talent acquisition is favourably influenced by cost-effectiveness, relative advantage, top management support, HR readiness, competitive pressure, and AI vendor support, according to this study. Security and privacy problems impede the use of AI technologies. It is discovered that task and technology features have an impact on the task and technology fit of AI technology for talent acquisition. Adoption and job technology fit have an impact on how effectively AI technology is used for hiring. The association between AI adoption and actual application in talent acquisition is found to be negatively impacted by stickiness to conventional methods of talent acquisition. The proposed model was empirically tested and revealed determinants of the uptake of AI technology and its real application for hiring.
11	AI adoption in the hiring process – important criteria and extent of AI adoption	AI, Extent, and Criteria for adoption	The results of this study indicate that human resources managers view information security and return on investment as two very important factors when thinking about the usage of AI in the hiring process. Adoption of AI for job sourcing and initial screening has been proven to be appropriate. And between before and after the COVID-19 pandemic problem started, the recruiting stage where AI can be deployed has become more appropriate. In light of altering external and internal circumstances, the findings and discussion enable businesses to make more informed decisions regarding the integration of AI into their hiring procedures.

12	Antecedents and outcomes of artificial intelligence adoption and application in the workplace: the socio-technical system theory perspective	AI, Antecedents and Outcomes	On order to capture the essence of AI's impact in the workplace, this paper evaluates the literature and develops a theoretically grounded conceptual framework based on socio-technical system theory. Acceptance and application of AI have antecedents in the personnel subsystem, technical subsystem, organisational structure subsystem, and environmental factors. Adoption and implementation of AI have an impact on outcomes for individuals, organisations, and employment.
13	AI-enabled recruiting in the war for talent	AI and Recruitment	Examine how, by bridging the gap between human resource management and military escalation literature, three key onset conditions associated with the adoption of AI-enabled recruiting tools have the potential to spark an arms race for such tools.
14	Factors that influence new-generation candidates to engage with and complete digital, AI-enabled recruiting	AI and Recruitment	In this study, researchers looked at how social media use, inherent benefits, fairness, and perceived trendiness affected job candidates' intents to participate in and finish digital, AI-enabled hiring processes.
15	AI-enabled recruiting: What is it and how should a manager use it?	AI and Recruitment	Despite several issues and worries, there is enough demand for AI and its potential in recruiting that working managers are looking for guidance on how to use and interact with AI-enabled recruiting solutions.
16	Allying with AI? Reactions toward human-based, AI/ML-based, and augmented hiring processes	Reaction towards AI in recruitment	In two between-subjects experiments, the researchers gathered online samples of participants (undergraduate students and Prolific panellists, respectively), offered them with vignettes illustrating various selection algorithms, and assessed how they reacted to them. The results impact how (and to whom) businesses should use AI/ML-based processes.
17	Intelligent recruitment: How to identify, select, and retain talents from around the world using artificial intelligence	AI and Recruitment	The approach of this study employed grounded theory, participant observation, and qualitative data gathering. The topic of the paper examines the effectiveness and constraints of various tools as well as their convergence through growing integration that results in the uberization of recruiting.
18	A Systematic Review of Artificial Intelligence and Hiring: Present Position and Future Research Areas	AI and Recruitment	200 research articles that were pertinent to AI in Hiring (AIHr) were discovered between 2010 and 2020 as a result of the study's literature evaluation. As a result, even if there have been research and papers written on the subject, the majority of them have not produced any certain conclusions about the use of AI in hiring. Similar to this, less study was conducted earlier in 2018 due to a lack of knowledge and experience with AI and its associated terminologies. Another significant aspect is that the majority of research is limited to the use of AI in entry-level recruitment and selection.
19	How Far Have We Come With The Study Of Artificial Intelligence For Recruitment Process		A systematic review of seven cited articles, five magazine articles, and twenty websites took into account the viewpoints of the topic and related fields. The study's findings complement previous research on AI-based recruitment processes and help provide a more complete picture of the subject and related domains.
20	Artificial Intelligence Chatbots are New Recruiters		The study exclusively uses secondary sources, including conceptual papers, peer-reviewed articles, and websites, to provide the current research. According to the survey, artificial intelligence chatbots are extremely effective tools in the hiring process and would be helpful in creating recruitment strategies for the sector. Additionally, it concentrates more on finding solutions to challenging problems in the hiring process. Although the use of artificial intelligence in hiring is growing among professionals, more research has to be done in this area. The study suggested potential directions for further research in the field of chatbots and recruiters.

21	AI in talent acquisition: a review of AI applications used in recruitment and selection		This study produced a number of conclusions. It started by listing 11 places in the R&S Process where AI can be applied. However, chatbots, screening software, and task automation technologies appear to be the three tools that practitioners currently rely on the most. Second, the bulk of companies using AI technologies are bigger, more technologically advanced, or both. Last but not least, despite the exponential growth of AI usage, businesses have not yet reached a tipping point because they are still reluctant to invest in the technology for R&S.
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V. FUTURE RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This study performed a comprehensive literature review to determine the extent to which artificial intelligence has permeated the human resource management function of recruitment and selection. It was discovered that the AI implementation in the recruitment function is still quite primitive. It was caused by the organisations' inability to place any faith in the new technology. There is a further scope for research by focusing on the research questions mentioned below:

- What are the causes of the organisations' lack of faith in the use of artificial intelligence in the recruitment and selection process?
- What are the factors that influence the application of artificial intelligence in the HR function of recruiting and selection?
- Why does the organization's recruitment and selection function only use artificial intelligence at the most fundamental level?

VI. CONCLUSION

Artificial intelligence is no longer a novel idea; it is now somehow present in all facets of business. Artificial intelligence has a significant role to play in the sourcing, screening, and prisoner interview phases of the recruiting and selection process in the field of human resources. The recruitment and selection industry has seen significant advancements in a number of software and technological areas, including (1) a social network with LinkedIn, (2) a MOOC with Udacity, (3) a serious game called Reveal from L'Oreal, (4) a chatbot named Ari from TextRecruit, and (5) a massive data analysis matching system with Randstad. One aspect that significantly affects the use of AI in the R&S domain is a lack of confidence. The lack of employee awareness and familiarity with the application and usage of AI is another barrier to the growth of the adoption of AI in Human Resource Management sectors, specifically with reference to Recruitment and selection. The conclusion drawn from the examination of all the material is that, if Artificial Intelligence is universally acknowledged and trusted to produce positive results, it has the potential to significantly increase the efficiency and accuracy of the recruitment process.

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